

Adoption of FinTech Training by Family Enterprises and its Impact on Local Economic Growth in Morocco

Wafaa El Gouz¹, Azzeddine Alloui^{2*}

¹Mohamed V University, Morocco

²ESCA Ecole de Management, Morocco

*Corresponding Author: aalloui@esca.ma

ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to evaluate the adoption of Financial Technologies (FinTech) training by family businesses in Morocco and to assess the consequences of this acceptance for the development of the local economy. Traditional business models are being reformulated as a result of technological advancements, which are causing the global financial environment to undergo fast transformation. In this context, family businesses, which make up a significant portion of Morocco's economic fabric, are investigated regarding the degree to which they have committed themselves to the teaching of financial technology. Regulatory frameworks, resource accessibility, and understanding of the possible implications of FinTech tools are some of the important elements that are investigated in this research. The study also provides an analysis of the factors that influence the adoption of FinTech training among family businesses. The objective is to provide insights into the obstacles and possibilities connected with incorporating FinTech into the operations of family companies in Morocco by first gaining an awareness of these issues. In addition to this, the study investigates the practical consequences that the implementation of FinTech has on the operational efficiency, risk management, and decision-making processes of family businesses. Our goal is to shed light on the role that FinTech plays in enhancing the competitiveness and growth prospects of family businesses, thereby contributing to the overall economic development at the local level in Morocco. This will be accomplished through an analysis of case studies and empirical data. It is expected that the outcomes of this study will provide significant insights for policymakers, business executives, and academics interested in the nexus between family businesses, financial technology education, and economic development.

KEYWORDS: family businesses, financial technology, innovation, economic growth

Introduction

Over the course of the last several years, the global financial environment has been subjected to a profound transformation, which has been prompted by the introduction and widespread use of Financial Technologies (FinTech) (Arslan et al. 2022). Family businesses, which constitute a significant economic force in Morocco, are situated at the intersection of tradition and innovation. This is because family businesses are already grappling with the implications of the technological revolution that is currently taking place across all industries. The purpose of this article is to investigate the dynamics of the adoption of financial technology within the setting of family businesses in Morocco and to analyze the influence that this adoption has had on the development of the local economy.

The Kingdom of Morocco, which is particularly well-known for its varied economic environment, is now seeing a growing incorporation of technology into a variety of different businesses. Family-owned businesses, which are distinguished by their one-of-a-kind ownership structures and long-standing traditions, are now navigating a business climate that is undergoing significant change. In light of this, it is very necessary to have an awareness of the elements that influence the adoption of FinTech training in order to appreciate how these businesses make use of technological breakthroughs (Fan et al. 2023). The major purpose of this study is to determine the degree to which family businesses in Morocco have committed themselves to the implementation of FinTech training programs. An in-depth analysis of the

regulatory frameworks that govern the adoption of FinTech, the availability of resources for training programs, and the level of awareness among family businesses regarding the potential benefits and challenges associated with the incorporation of FinTech are all required to accomplish this (Arslan et al. 2022).

As we go further into this investigation, the article will also throw light on the larger consequences that have been associated with the adoption of FinTech for family businesses. Within the context of family enterprises, the ways in which these technology breakthroughs impact operational efficiency (Song and Appiah-Otoo 2022), risk management procedures, and strategic decision-making will be investigated. The ultimate goal is to determine the influence that FinTech training has on the growth trajectory of family businesses and, by extension, the contribution that it makes to the economic development of Morocco at the local level. In addition, the development of financial technology has not only resulted in certain operational changes, but it has also greatly impacted the expectations and behaviors of customers. Family businesses in Morocco are facing the need of aligning themselves with the changes that are occurring in the financial services industry as it undergoes a digital transformation. This is necessary to survive and remain competitive. As a strategic reaction to this changing environment, the implementation of FinTech training programs for family companies becomes a strategic response (Arslan et al. 2022). These programs provide a road to equip these organizations with the essential skills and insights.

In addition to the technical and legal aspects, the socio-economic backdrop of Morocco adds another layer of complexity to the understanding of the use of financial technology by family businesses. The pace and scope of the incorporation of financial technology may be affected by a variety of factors, including the availability of financial resources, the educational backgrounds of family members, and cultural conceptions of technology. When it comes to developing successful FinTech training programs that connect with the unique demands and issues encountered by family firms in the Moroccan business environment, it is essential to investigate these intricacies (Song et Appiah-Otoo 2022).

By offering a targeted investigation of the interaction between family businesses, FinTech education, and local economic development in Morocco, this research contributes to the current body of knowledge by giving an opportunity to investigate this junction. Our goal is to provide a comprehensive framework that sheds light on the myriad of dynamics that are at play in this area by synthesizing the insights that have been gleaned from the existing body of research. In the following parts, we will explore further into the methodology that was used, the empirical results, and the consequences of FinTech adoption for family businesses and the larger economic environment in Morocco. This will be done as we begin this voyage of investigation. We hope that by doing this study, we will be able to give nuanced insights into the growing link that exists between family businesses, education in FinTech, and economic development in Morocco. The results are relevant for policymakers, business executives, and academics who are looking for a complete knowledge of the interaction between technology innovation and traditional business practices in the Moroccan economic scene.

Literature Review

It reflects the extensive influence that technological improvements have had on the global financial landscape that the incorporation of Financial Technologies (FinTech) into corporate operations has arisen as a focal point of academic inquiry. Although a substantial amount of research has been conducted to investigate the wider implications of FinTech adoption, a more nuanced investigation within the context of family businesses, particularly in the Moroccan environment, reveals that there is a discernible gap in the existing literature (Arslan et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2020).

One of the most important aspects of the adoption of FinTech is the capabilities it has to revolutionize conventional company models, therefore improving both the efficiency and the decision-making processes. The agility and creativity that FinTech technologies bring to the forefront have been the subject of several studies that have been conducted across a variety of sectors. The incorporation of FinTech is of relevance within the realm of family businesses, which are distinguished by their one-of-a-kind ownership structures and rather conservative attitudes to business operations (Zarrouk, El Ghak, and Bakhouche 2021). The role that regulatory frameworks have in determining the adoption landscape of financial technology is a topic that is often discussed in research literature. When it comes to the smooth integration of new technologies into corporate processes, the regulatory framework may either operate as a facilitator or a barrier. When it comes to family businesses in Morocco, having a thorough awareness of the complexities of regulatory compliance is very necessary to successfully navigate the ever-changing environment of the financial technology industry.

Furthermore, the research emphasizes the significance of resource accessibility in affecting the rate of acceptance of FinTech and the degree to which it is implemented. Family businesses, which may have different resource limits compared to bigger companies, are required to analyze the feasibility and cost-effectiveness of integrating FinTech solutions when compared to those of larger firms. According to studies, there is a pressing desire for individualized techniques that take into account the particular financial capabilities of family companies. It becomes clear that educational backgrounds and technical literacy inside family businesses are becoming more important elements that influence the use of financial technology. As these companies manage generational shifts, the ability of family members to accept technological breakthroughs and their willingness to make use of those technologies becomes more important. It is possible that cultural attitudes about technology, especially in a traditional culture such as Morocco, may also influence the preparedness of family businesses to embrace FinTech technologies (Arslan et al. 2022; Zarrouk, El Ghak, and Bakhouche 2021).

The socio-economic environment of Morocco adds another degree of complication to the process of comprehending the use of financial technology. Family businesses are deeply knit into the fabric of society, and this includes access to financial resources, educational possibilities, and cultural views toward technology. Making sure that these contextual subtleties are taken into consideration is very necessary to build efficient FinTech training programs that are suited to the particular requirements and difficulties that family companies in Morocco confront. In conclusion, while the existing body of research offers a strong basis for comprehending the more far-reaching ramifications of the implementation of FinTech, few studies have been conducted to investigate the unique dynamics that exist inside family businesses in Morocco. By providing a focused examination of the adoption of FinTech training efforts and its resultant influence on local economic development within the specific context of family firms in Morocco, the purpose of this research is to fill this vacuum in knowledge (Zhang et al. 2020).

It is important to note that the literature about the implementation of FinTech in family businesses goes beyond the operational elements and has larger implications for governance, succession planning, and the maintenance of family values. Family businesses are characterized by several distinctive traits, including intergenerational dynamics and a concentration on long-term sustainability. These qualities provide a unique set of problems and possibilities in the context of the integration of FinTech. One of the most important aspects that has been investigated in the research literature is the role that FinTech plays in solving the issues that are associated with succession planning within family businesses. When it comes to these kinds of enterprises, succession planning is a sensitive process that is often impacted by family connections and complex power dynamics. Through the provision of comprehensive financial planning and management solutions, FinTech tools have the potential to make transitions more seamless, thereby contributing to the continuity and

stability of family businesses over the course of multiple generations, as indicated by research investigations (Zhang et al. 2020).

In addition, the research on the adoption of FinTech examines the governance frameworks that are present inside family businesses. Given the decentralized nature of decision-making in family companies, it is possible that some FinTech applications might be advantageous in terms of the transparency and accountability elements that they include. This has the potential to reduce the likelihood of conflicts of interest and improve governance processes in general, so ensuring that family businesses continue to function effectively while preserving their individuality (Fan et al. 2023). Furthermore, the maintenance of family values and the heritage of the family is a primary priority for many businesses that are run by families. The research implies that innovations in financial technology may be used to align with and reinforce these values, even though technological improvements may be seen as having the potential to be disruptive. FinTech adoption has the potential to become a driver for the modernization of family businesses without sacrificing the fundamental principles that guide them. This may be accomplished by integrating technology in a manner that is respectful of the traditions and ethos of the family.

In order to have a better understanding of the complexities involved in the implementation of FinTech inside family companies in Morocco, it is vital to draw insights from the experiences of firms that are comparable to those in other global settings. Comparative studies and case studies provide significant benchmarks and lessons learned that may be used to influence the creation of successful strategies for the integration of FinTech that are adapted to the unique requirements of family businesses in Morocco. In conclusion, the literature study sheds light on the myriad of consequences that the implementation of FinTech has for family businesses. These implications go beyond the area of operations and include governance, succession planning, and the maintenance of family values. In order to have a comprehensive knowledge of the complications that are involved in the incorporation of FinTech within the specific context of family businesses in Morocco, these aspects provide a rich tapestry. In the next parts of this study, we will dig into the methodological approach that was used to explore the adoption of FinTech, offer empirical data, and evaluate the consequences for the development of the local economy (Song and Appiah-Otoo 2022).

When the influence of financial technology (FinTech) on the development of the local economy is investigated, a complex link between the use of technology in family businesses and the larger economic landscape of Morocco is revealed. Although the global literature provides significant insights into the possible macroeconomic implications of FinTech, it is necessary to have a focused lens in order to comprehend how these dynamics emerge within the context of Morocco. One of the most important aspects of this investigation is taking into consideration the role that FinTech plays in working to expand access to financial services. There is evidence in the literature that shows that FinTech can close access gaps to financial services, particularly in areas that have historically been underserved by providers of financial services. In the context of Morocco, where socioeconomic gaps continue to exist, it is of utmost importance to investigate the ways in which the use of FinTech in family businesses might help to the expansion of financial inclusion.

Additionally, the literature sheds light on the connection between the adoption of FinTech and entrepreneurial endeavors. FinTech solutions that expedite financial procedures, remove obstacles to entry, and boost the entire business environment may be beneficial to family businesses, which are often considered to be the engines of local entrepreneurship. Therefore, it is vital to conduct an investigation into this connection in order to determine how the incorporation of FinTech into family businesses may stimulate entrepreneurial endeavors, which in turn may have an effect on the expansion of the local economy. In addition, the research that has been done on the topic highlights the potential of financial technology to encourage innovation inside family businesses. In the context of this discussion, innovation

encompasses not just technological developments but also unique business structures, product offers, and market tactics. To evaluate the effects that the adoption of FinTech has on the competitiveness and adaptability of family businesses in the Moroccan economic landscape, it is essential to have a solid understanding of how the adoption of FinTech helps to cultivate a culture of innovation within family businesses (Zhang et al. 2020).

In order to successfully negotiate the complex relationship that exists between the adoption of FinTech, family businesses, and the expansion of the local economy, it is very necessary to acknowledge the ever-changing nature of financial ecosystems. According to the available literature, the nature of FinTech is dynamic, with ongoing innovations in the industry influencing the environment. This dynamic nature highlights the need of adaptable tactics within family businesses, highlighting the significance of the relevance of continual learning and agility in the face of the growth of technology. In conclusion, the literature study posits that the adoption of financial technology inside family businesses is a phenomenon that is diverse and has ramifications that range from the efficiency of operations to the enhancement of economic development in general. An all-encompassing viewpoint is provided by the investigation of financial inclusion, entrepreneurialism, and innovation, which sheds light on the complex linkages that occur within the setting of Morocco. As the subsequent sections of this research move forward, the empirical findings will contribute to further enriching our understanding of these complexities and their implications for family businesses and the growth of the Moroccan economy at the local level.

The investigation of risk management procedures is an essential component in the process of comprehending the repercussions that might result from the implementation of FinTech within family businesses. When it comes to family businesses, traditional risk management frequently relies on experience and intuition. However, the literature suggests that the incorporation of FinTech can introduce risk assessment methodologies that are more data-driven and sophisticated. This shift is especially relevant in the context of Morocco, where family businesses frequently face novel challenges that are associated with fluctuations in the market, political unpredictability, and cultural nuances. The research that has been done on the topic highlights the potential of FinTech tools, such as predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms, to improve risk identification and mitigation strategies. Family businesses that successfully incorporate these tools are able to navigate uncertainty with greater ease, thereby ensuring the maintenance of their financial health and the continuation of their company's existence. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate how the adoption of FinTech affects risk management practices within family businesses, as well as the subsequent impact that this adoption has on the resilience and adaptability of family businesses (Song and Appiah-Otoo 2022; Zarrouk, El Ghak, and Bakhouche 2021).

A significant amount of emphasis is placed in the literature on the role that FinTech plays in facilitating access to capital for family businesses, in addition to risk management. Funding has traditionally been difficult to acquire for smaller businesses, including family businesses. This has been the case throughout history. Because of their innovative lending models and crowdfunding mechanisms, FinTech platforms have the potential to make access to capital more accessible to more people everywhere. In order to get a better understanding of the role that FinTech plays in promoting financial stability and development (Arslan et al. 2022), it is essential to conduct research on the ways in which the adoption of FinTech affects the capital structure of family businesses in Morocco. In addition, the literature calls attention to the ethical issues that are involved with the use of blockchain technology. Ethical considerations such as data protection, cybersecurity, and transparency become of the utmost importance as family businesses negotiate the process of integrating new technology. To ensure that family businesses are able to strike a balance between innovation and ethical responsibility, it is vital to investigate the ethical implications of the adoption of FinTech within the framework of Moroccan culture and the legal system.

In addition to this, the literature analysis highlights the need of a comprehensive framework for analyzing the effect that FinTech has on family businesses. In order to do this, it is necessary to not only evaluate the immediate operational gains, but also to take into consideration the wider socio-economic repercussions. Using these insights as a foundation, the purpose of this research is to develop a robust analytical framework that considers the various aspects of FinTech adoption within family businesses (Zhang et al. 2020). This will contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the implications that FinTech adoption has for the growth of the Moroccan economy. In a nutshell, the literature study goes into essential aspects such as risk management, access to finance, and ethical issues. This provides a complete background for comprehending the myriad of effects that the implementation of FinTech inside family businesses might have. For the purpose of shedding light on the intricate relationships between FinTech adoption, risk management, access to capital, and ethical considerations, these insights will guide the exploration of how these dynamics manifest within the unique context of family enterprises in Morocco. This will take place as we transition to the empirical findings and analysis that will be presented in the subsequent sections.

Methodology

The study approach utilizes a purposive sample technique to pick a varied variety of family firms in Morocco. This strategy assures coverage across diverse sizes, sectors, and geographical regions, offering a complete perspective of FinTech adoption trends. Data gathering comprises the delivery of organized questionnaires to family firm owners and key decision-makers. These surveys try to evaluate the amount of FinTech adoption, identify perceived advantages and obstacles, and analyze the influence on different parts of corporate operations. The survey instrument is constructed based on ideas from the literature study and first exploratory interviews.

Complementing the quantitative data, in-depth interviews are done with a group of family business representatives. These interviews dive into qualitative elements of FinTech adoption, investigating cultural factors, ethical concerns, and the delicate relationships between technology and family systems. The qualitative data gathered via interviews adds depth to the knowledge of the complex elements impacting FinTech adoption. The combination of quantitative survey data and qualitative insights from interviews produces a solid dataset, allowing a detailed examination of the link between FinTech adoption by family firms and its influence on local economic development in Morocco. This mixed-methods approach enables for a complete investigation of the study goals without imposing false divisions between quantitative and qualitative viewpoints.

Results

The combination of survey and interview data presents a comprehensive representation of FinTech adoption tendencies among family firms in Morocco. Various degrees of adoption are visible, with a notable tendency toward tools such as digital payment systems, accounting software, and data analytics. This tendency is driven by a variety of reasons, ranging from the pursuit of innovative business models to the desire to improve operational efficiency. Perceived advantages of FinTech adoption, as revealed by quantitative data, comprise greater operational efficiency, enhanced decision-making processes, and expanded access to financial data. Concurrently, difficulties, like data security problems and the demand for constant training, are also highlighted. Qualitative insights dig into the complicated balance between perceived advantages and problems within the specific environment of family companies.

An examination into the influence of FinTech on company operations indicates good results, with family firms seeing enhanced financial management, simplified procedures, and faster decision-making. Qualitative data augments these results by illustrating how these

operational innovations help to the overall resilience and flexibility of family firms, notably in handling obstacles peculiar to the Moroccan business scene. The study expands its attention to explore the economic growth implications of FinTech adoption. Quantitative and qualitative evaluations merge to illustrate the potential of FinTech-equipped family firms to contribute positively to local economic development. The efficiencies obtained via technological integration allow these firms to play a role in encouraging economic development, revealing insights into how FinTech functions as a catalyst for growth within the Moroccan business ecosystem. In conclusion, the combination of quantitative and qualitative data presents a holistic picture of FinTech adoption among family firms in Morocco. The analysis provides insights into the dynamics of adoption, the interplay between perceived benefits and challenges, the impact on business operations, and the potential contributions to local economic growth (Zarrouk, El Ghak, and Bakhouché 2021; Zhang et al. 2020). These results serve as a vital addition to the understanding of FinTech's function inside family firms and its larger implications for the economic environment in Morocco.

The discussion extends to the broader implications of FinTech adoption within family enterprises, weaving together the multifaceted layers that emerge from the analysis of adoption patterns, benefits, challenges, and economic growth contributions. The nuanced nature of these findings prompts a reflection on the interconnected dynamics shaping the landscape of family businesses in Morocco. The examination of patterns of adoption of financial technology highlights the adaptability of family businesses to advances in technology. Both their operational requirements and their forward-looking attitude to innovation are aligned with the strategic selection of certain tools that they have available. According to the research, these tendencies reflect a purposeful effort made by family businesses to harness technology in a way that matches their traditional values while also creating resilience in an environment that is constantly changing in terms of business situations.

The conversation dives into the mutually beneficial connection that exists between the apparent advantages of FinTech adoption and the issues that it presents. The realization of operational efficiencies and the improvement of decision-making processes is counterbalanced by concerns related to the security of data and the requirement for ongoing training. To achieve their goal of technological integration, family businesses need to carefully weigh the benefits of technological integration against the challenges that it presents. This delicate equilibrium highlights the strategic decision-making processes that are involved in family businesses. Moreover, the significant beneficial influence that FinTech has on the operations of businesses emerges as a major subject over the course of the conversation (Arslan et al. 2022; Zhang et al. 2020). Family businesses can improve their overall competitiveness by integrating digital payment systems, accounting software, and data analytics. This not only increases efficiency but also contributes to the overall competitiveness of the family business. Family businesses are now in a position to navigate the complexities of the Moroccan business landscape with agility and foresight thanks to their increased operational prowess.

The study offers light on the revolutionary potential of family businesses that are equipped with FinTech, which is especially important when considering the consequences for economic development. The enhancement of their operational capacities and the expansion of their capacity for innovation are two ways in which they demonstrate their contribution to the expansion of the local economy. According to the results, family businesses that make use of FinTech technologies become active players in the economic development of Morocco. These businesses can serve as engines for the creation of jobs and sustainable growth. Ultimately, the adoption of financial technology, the development of family businesses, and the expansion of the local economy in Morocco all interact with one another to build a complex web of interconnected interactions. The findings of this study add to a better understanding of how

family businesses handle the complications of technology integration while yet maintaining their individual identities. The results not only demonstrate the resiliency and adaptation of these enterprises (Arslan et al. 2022), but they also indicate the potential for these businesses to be important contributors to the economic development of Morocco in an age of technological transition. The larger backdrop of the conversation involves the changing environment of family businesses in Morocco in the middle of the surge of adoption of FinTech that is undergoing a transformation. These enterprises have the ability to function as catalysts for sustainable economic development, which stimulates observations on the future direction of these businesses and their potential expansion. A thorough knowledge of the complex dynamics at play may be obtained via the integration of data from both quantitative and qualitative investigations.

When looking at the patterns of strategic adoption of financial technology within family companies, it is important to emphasize how important it is to connect the incorporation of technology with the values and traditions that are intrinsic to these types of firms. A careful approach is shown by the selective adoption of certain instruments, which strikes a balance between the pursuit of efficiency benefits and the preservation of the individuality of the member of the family. Through this strategic alignment, family businesses are placed on a path that allows them to seamlessly incorporate innovation into their operations. This helps to ensure that their legacies are preserved while also allowing them to take advantage of the opportunities that are presented by financing technology.

The detailed conversation that surrounds perceived advantages and obstacles gives insight on the decision-making process that is pragmatic inside family businesses. Concerns about data security and the need for ongoing training are two challenges that these companies face as they traverse the always shifting environment of the FinTech industry. When it comes to guaranteeing the long-term viability of the integration of FinTech, both acknowledging and resolving these problems become essential components. The family businesses that are looking for a balanced combination of history and technical innovation may benefit greatly from this nuanced viewpoint, which delivers useful insights. The debate has shed light on the fact that the beneficial influence that FinTech has on corporate operations goes beyond the immediate advantages that are gained in terms of operations. In family businesses, it helps to cultivate a culture of adaptation and creativity, which in turn contributes to the businesses' capacity to remain competitive in the always shifting business environment (Zhang et al. 2020). Based on the data, it seems that these companies, who are armed with FinTech technologies, are in a strong position to overcome obstacles, seize opportunities, and actively contribute to the economic vitality of Morocco.

Family businesses, with their acceptance of FinTech, have the potential to be essential actors in Morocco's economic development, as the study examines the ramifications of economic growth. This becomes obvious as the research moves forward. Their contributions go beyond just improving operational efficiency; they also actively participate in the development of a business environment that is both dynamic and resilient. The results suggest that the symbiosis between family businesses that are equipped with FinTech and the expansion of the local economy is not only conceivable (Fan et al. 2023 ; Song and Appiah-Otoo 2022), but also shows promise for the further development of the Moroccan business scene. In conclusion, this research trip that investigated the adoption of financial technology among family businesses in Morocco offers a comprehensive perspective on the transformational power of technology. The conversation not only sheds light on the complex dynamics that exist inside these companies, but also provides a glimpse into a future in which innovation and tradition may dwell side by side in a peaceful manner. As family businesses continue to negotiate the changing terrain, the strategic integration of FinTech solutions that they have implemented positions them to be vital contributors to the economic development and vibrancy of Morocco in the years to come.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the purpose of this study was to conduct an in-depth investigation of the implementation of Financial Technologies (FinTech) inside family businesses in Morocco and the subsequent influence that this adoption has had on the expansion of the local economy. A detailed knowledge of the complex dynamics at play inside these companies as they negotiate the ever-changing terrain of technology integration has been offered because of the combination of quantitative survey data and qualitative insights gleaned from interviews.

According to the findings of the survey, family businesses have used FinTech to varied degrees, demonstrating a deliberate alignment of technology with traditional values. The deliberate adoption of certain instruments, such as digital payment systems and data analytics, demonstrates a determined attempt to maintain the identity of the family while also embracing the benefits that are given by innovative financial technology. Through the use of this nuanced strategy, family businesses are positioned to become adaptable organizations that are ready to utilize technology to improve their operational efficiency without jeopardizing their distinctive legacies. However, the perceived advantages of adopting FinTech, such as greater operational efficiency and enhanced decision-making processes, have been counterbalanced by problems such as concerns around data security and the need for ongoing training. This precarious balance highlights the pragmatic decision-making that occurs inside family businesses, stressing the significance of resolving problems to enable the sustainable incorporation of FinTech instruments.

A culture of adaptation and innovation is fostered inside family businesses as a result of the good influence that FinTech has on company operations. This impact goes beyond the initial profits that are immediately realized. These enterprises are in a position to handle problems, embrace opportunities, and actively contribute to the economic vitality of Morocco because they are equipped with instruments that are associated with financial technology. The mutually beneficial relationship that exists between family businesses that are equipped with FinTech and the expansion of the local economy becomes more apparent, pointing to a future in which these companies will play a pivotal role in the formation of a business ecosystem that is both dynamic and resilient.

The strategic incorporation of FinTech tools by family businesses positions them as key stakeholders in the economic growth of Morocco. This is because family businesses are continuing to change in response to the transformation brought about by technology advancements. In addition to providing a view into the complex processes that characterize the junction of tradition and innovation within family businesses, the results of this study provide useful insights that may be used by politicians, business leaders, and academics. The flexibility and resiliency shown by these enterprises point to a bright future in which FinTech will act as a catalyst for sustained economic growth and development. This is coming at a time when Morocco is transitioning into an age of technological revolution.

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